

OMNIS: Semantic RAN Slicing via Dynamic Split Neural Networks

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Abstract—Edge computing enables resource-constrained devices to execute machine learning applications via task offloading. To this aim, radio access network (RAN) slicing is instrumental to provide the necessary network resources. However, current RAN slicing approaches rely on static computing models, thereby constraining their ability to leverage the dynamic semantic data representation capabilities enabled by recent neural architectures. In this paper, we propose OMNIS, a semantic RAN slicing framework for edge computing built on dynamic split neural models. OMNIS embeds a dynamic form of neural compression paired with adaptive data encoding for task offloading, enabling flexible communication payload and computing options. We explicitly study the interplay between neural compression and information quantization in computer vision tasks and design a novel “Box” quantization scheme that improves resiliency to bit errors as a function of compression rate. Considering partial observability and differing objectives of mobile devices and the edge server, we formulate neural gate control and resource slicing optimization problems and solve them via multi-agent contextual multi-armed bandits and convex optimization algorithms. Experimental results show that OMNIS improves inference accuracy by up to 22.85% and reduces quality of service violations by up to 10x. The evaluation code is available at <https://github.com/qlt315/OMNIS>.

Index Terms—Edge computing, machine learning, resource allocation, wireless communications

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid rise of machine learning (ML)-powered applications, including real-time video analytics, autonomous driving, and augmented reality, has introduced latency-sensitive and computationally intensive workloads, often involving complex neural networks and large data volumes [1]. As a result, resource-constrained mobile devices (MDs) face challenges in meeting quality of service (QoS) requirements. By offloading computing-intensive ML tasks to edge servers (ES), edge computing has emerged as a paradigm to support real-time inference by significantly reducing task execution latency [2]. In this context, radio access network (RAN) slicing plays a critical role in supporting edge computing by enabling the flexible and efficient provisioning of communication and computing resources. However, most RAN slicing frameworks for edge computing directly transmit the raw sensor data and perform inference on the ES [3], [4]. Such an approach may require large data rates to make edge computing functional. For example, in image-based tasks using the COCO dataset [5], transmitting JPEG-compressed images can require hundreds of Kilobits per frame. Some recent frameworks [2] –

Fig. 1: Comparison of existing RAN slicing frameworks for edge computing and OMNIS’s approach: (a) Offloading with neural network partitioning [2]; (b) Offloading with static data compression [7], [8]; (c) OMNIS.

see Fig. 1(a) – *split* deep neural network architectures and transmit the tensors produced by a set of neural layers executed by the MD. However, this approach may result in excessive bandwidth consumption as well; for instance, in ResNet-50 [6] the intermediate feature map at the “conv3” layer has a size of 3.1 MB when stored in FP32 format. The works in [7], [8] exemplify two other classes of contributions based on semantic communications – see Fig. 1(b). Specifically, [7] relies on static neural networks, such as joint source-channel coding via autoencoders, which lacks adaptability under fluctuating bit error rates (BER), as different BER levels can degrade inference performance to varying degrees. [8], instead, introduces an adjustable compression factor, allowing for dynamic semantic control over data reduction. However, none of these methods explicitly define how to implement such flexible compression, leaving a gap in practical deployment.

To address these issues, we propose a novel semantic RAN slicing framework called OMNIfacet Slicing (OMNIS). OMNIS connects semantic RAN slicing to a new generation of neural models: dynamic neural networks, an umbrella that includes multi-branch architectures. Notably, in this paper we develop a new class of dynamic neural networks that focuses flexibility in how the input data is neurally compressed into a compact latent space and quantized¹. At a high level, on the MD side, the neural model we build has branches

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¹We use “neural compression” for the neural encoding process and “compression” to denote the combined process of neural encoding and quantization.

Fig. 2: Accuracy vs. payload size for different quantization methods at SNR equal to 3 dB (left) and 10 dB (right).

that correspond to supervised in-model neural compression encoder-decoder structures chained with a set of quantization options – see Fig. 1(c). The different branches, whose output is encoded with low-density parity check (LDPC) codes to obtain a specific data payload, offer a tradeoff between compression on one hand and resilience to bit errors and task performance on the other. After transmission over the wireless channel, the data is then decoded, decompressed at the ES, and then used for inference. *The result is an extremely flexible semantic data representation and processing pipeline that can boost the overall system performance and efficiency when combined with RAN resource slicing.*

To better highlight the impact of data compression on inference performance under different transmission conditions, we conducted an illustrative experiment. Fig. 2 shows the semantic segmentation accuracy, trained on the COCO dataset [5], versus transmission payload size under varying values of signal to noise ratio (SNR). The neural network model used to generate the results in Fig. 2 is detailed in Sec. IV, while the parameter settings are given in Sec. VI. Notably, we use a split deep neural network [9] where the model is modified to include an encoder/decoder structure neurally compressing the data into a latent space. The tensor is then quantized using the “standard” (STD) quantization method, meaning that we quantize the 32-bit values tensor representation using a direct normalization and conversion to 8-bit integer values [10]. 3, 6, and 12 denote the number of feature channels output from the neural encoder, with higher numbers indicating lower quantization levels. We apply LDPC coding with coding rates (payload size/total data size) $\{0, 2/3, 5/6\}$ to the compressed output of the neural encoder embedded in the models. Thus, the payload size is determined by the number of feature channel, the quantization levels, and the LDPC coding rate.

This preliminary evaluation shows that accuracy increases with data payload up to a point, after which it plateaus. This is more evident at high SNR, where adding more bits increases the transmitted data, but accuracy remains constant. Both MD’s channel quality and payload size significantly impact accuracy. Poor channel conditions increase BER, leading to erroneous data for inference at the ES, while larger payload sizes improve accuracy but clearly increase transmission overhead. These results thus show that flexibility in how data is compressed is essential to obtain functional – both communication and computing – pipelines.

Our contributions can thus be summarized as follows:

- We propose OMNIS, a semantic RAN slicing framework for edge computing. OMNIS exploits a dynamic split DNN architecture that can produce flexible compressed data representations designed to support inference tasks. The neural network branches include advanced supervised neural encoder-

decoder structures, paired with strategies for quantization of the data latent representation.

- In this context, we propose a new quantization approach to improve the tradeoff between compression on one hand and resilience to bit errors and task performance on the other, in channel regimes where current strategies are ineffective. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper to consider such a tradeoff in the design of dynamic split DNNs and semantic communications.

- To balance transmission efficiency and inference accuracy, we formulate two optimization problems for MDs and ES (resp.), considering their partial view of the system and different objectives. MDs aim to maximize their own task accuracy by controlling the dynamic split DNN, while the ES seeks to maximize the minimum accuracy across MDs for fairness. To solve these NP-hard problems, we design a multi-agent distributed optimization framework, where each MD acts as a contextual multi-armed bandit agent using Bayesian optimization to select the best neural branch, and the ES allocates resources via block coordinated descent (BCD).

- We perform an extensive evaluation demonstrating the effectiveness of OMNIS. Compared to state-of-the-art RAN slicing schemes, OMNIS improves inference accuracy by up to 22.85% while reducing the QoS constraint violation probability by up to 10x.

II. RELATED WORK

Mobile Edge Computing. The most recent works aim at optimizing task offloading to the edge, via binary or partial offloading. In binary offloading, tasks are indivisible, requiring full local execution or complete offloading [11]. Partial offloading (or split computing) splits inference, executing a portion of it locally and offloading the rest. [12]. Some studies jointly optimize task offloading and resource slicing [13], but adopt a binary offloading model, thus limiting the flexibility in determining the communication and computing model. Conversely, partial offloading approaches often assume simplistic and non-adaptive task partition strategies. OMNIS presents an explicit connection between dynamic split neural networks, compression, encoding and resource slicing, ensuring robust and deployable offloading across diverse network conditions and application demands.

RAN Slicing. It virtualizes network resources into isolated partitions for flexible allocation. Examples of proposed strategies include [14], which leverages deep reinforcement learning (DRL) for content caching and mode selection in hotspot and vehicular scenarios. [15] models slicing as a congestion game with a unique Nash equilibrium (NE), and designs two fully distributed algorithms to converge to the NE without exposing sensitive tenant information. Also, [16] first identifies MDs with satisfiable QoS and then jointly optimizes slice association and bandwidth allocation to minimize resource consumption. However, existing frameworks are designed for static neural networks, thus failing to leverage important synergies between the adaptation capabilities of ML tasks and resource allocation. OMNIS overcomes these limitations by integrating dynamic neural networks and jointly optimizing

Fig. 3: System model of OMNIS.

RAN resource allocation and DNN branch control, enabling personalized provisioning and task-specific customization.

Semantic Communications. Semantic communications leverage ML-driven data compression to extract and transmit only the most relevant information. For instance, VQ-DeepSC [17] uses ML-based transceivers and adversarial training to extract multi-scale semantic features for image transmission. Similarly, [18] introduces RL-based adaptive semantic coding to preserve task-relevant information while discarding less critical data. [19], instead, formalizes a rate-distortion tradeoff, proposing dynamic neural networks for variable-length feature encoding depending on channel conditions. SEM-O-RAN [8], the closest work to ours, enables semantic RAN slicing for task offloading. Through a greedy algorithm, it optimizes data compression and the use of networking and computing resources. However, SEM-O-RAN does not specify the exact approach for data compression, nor does it account for the impact of wireless transmission errors on accuracy. Other works use static neural networks, whereas OMNIS employs dynamic neural networks that flexibly balance compression ratio and accuracy, enhancing resource utilization and efficiency, especially on unreliable radio channels.

III. OMNIS SYSTEM MODEL

The system model of OMNIS, depicted in Fig. 3, includes an edge computing-enabled RAN, consisting of a multi-antenna base station integrated with an ES and a set $\mathcal{M}=\{1, \dots, M\}$ of multi-antenna MDs distributed across the coverage area. Each MD $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and the ES are equipped with ρ^m and ρ^e antennas (resp.). The system operates in time slots indexed by $t=0, \dots, T$. In each time frame, composed of multiple time slots, each MD processes a computer vision job containing multiple inference tasks, where each task corresponds to processing a segment of data and performing inference within a single time slot. For instance, in the video surveillance application, the inference job of each MD is to process a video stream, with each task corresponding to analyzing a single video frame. The MD generates the ML inference task based on data collected from cameras. The task encapsulates various contextual information, including the MD's QoS requirements and preferences, and its computational capacity, channel conditions, and a summary of the data size to be processed.

In OMNIS, the MDs use a dynamic split DNN composed of multiple branches, which are dynamically selected by a gate unit. Each branch includes a dynamic split DNN sub-model designed with an advanced encoder-decoder architecture. As detailed later, the characteristics of the encoder-decoder control the tradeoff between compression gain on the one hand

and resilience to bit errors and task performance on the other. Each branch—or sub-model—consists of two parts: the head model on the MD side and the tail model on the ES side (detailed in Sec. IV). The head model is responsible for extracting semantic features from the raw data, compressing the features and then performing channel coding before transmission to the tail model on the ES via the multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) wireless channel. The tail model realizes the inverse process of the head model and generates the inference results, which are then returned to the MDs.

At the MD side, an optimization engine controls the gate unit of the dynamic split DNN model, using the task context as input. This enables the use of sub-models with varying compression (i.e., neural compression and quantization) capabilities. At the ES, a RAN controller (i) dynamically allocates bandwidth to MDs for their sending head model outputs, and (ii) assigns computing resources to support the execution of their tail models, optimizing both communication and computation efficiency. The controller is also responsible for adjusting the MDs' channel coding rate. Thus, as detailed in Sec. V, *OMNIS enables gate unit control and RAN resource slicing in a distributed and context-aware manner.*

The main OMNIS components are described below.

A. Mobile Device Computing Model

In each time slot t , the inference task generated by MD $m \in \mathcal{M}$ has specific QoS requirements, denoted as $\{\tau_m^{th}(t), E_m^{th}(t), \omega_m^l(t), \omega_m^e(t)\}$, where $\tau_m^{th}(t)$ and $E_m^{th}(t)$ are the expected latency and energy consumption targets, respectively. The preference weights $\omega_m^l(t)$ and $\omega_m^e(t)$ reflect MD m 's latency and energy priorities, e.g., a drone may prioritize low latency with a higher $\omega_m^l(t)$, while an IoT sensor may prioritize energy efficiency with a higher $\omega_m^e(t)$. Due to task variability, strict adherence to these targets may not always be possible, so violations are allowed to ensure task completion. The gate unit, based on the optimization engine, selects a specific branch (detailed in Sec. V), then feeds the raw data X into the head model of the branch, where it is neurally compressed and quantized. The quantized bit stream $x_m^c(t)$ then undergoes channel coding and modulation. Based on the gate unit, OMNIS enables dynamically adapting the quantization method $\beta_m(t)$ and the feature channel size $\lambda_m(t)$, based on each MD's wireless channel conditions and task requirements. The local computing latency of MD m in time slot t is given by: $\tau_m^l(t) = \psi_m^h(t) / (f_m^l c_m^l \chi_m^l)$, where $\psi_m^h(t)$ is the FLOPs of the head model, f_m^l , c_m^l , and χ_m^l represent the GPU frequency, number of GPU cores, and FLOPs per cycle per core of MD m , respectively. Given the GPU-dependent power

consumption coefficient, ζ_m^l , the local energy consumption is: $E_m^l(t) = \zeta_m^l (f_m^l)^3 \cdot \tau_m^l(t) = \zeta_m^l (f_m^l)^2 \psi_m^h(t) / c_m^l \chi_m^l$.

B. Transmission Model

To ensure reliable radio transmission, the compressed and quantized data stream $\mathbf{x}_m^c(t)$ undergoes channel encoding (e.g., using LDPC coding), which adds redundancy to reduce BER by detecting and correcting errors caused by the wireless channel. After channel encoding, modulation maps the bits onto symbols for transmission over the MIMO channel. In OMNIS, the channel coding rate $\phi_m(t) \in \Phi$ is dynamically adjusted based on channel conditions, task requirements, and quantization parameters of MD $m \in \mathcal{M}$. This flexibility allows OMNIS to balance transmission reliability and efficiency.

Let $\mathbf{x}_m^t(t)$ be the transmitted modulated bit stream of MD m and $\mathbf{H}_m(t)$ the wireless channel matrix between the ES and the MD m in time slot t . We consider a flat fading channel throughout each slot. Imperfect channel state information (CSI) is assumed due to noise, estimation errors, and channel variations. The estimated channel matrix is $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_m(t) = \mathbf{H}_m(t) + \mathbf{H}_m^e(t)$, where $\mathbf{H}_m^e(t)$ is the error matrix, modeled as zero-mean Gaussian noise with variance σ^h . To mitigate intra-cell interference, the ES divides the bandwidth into orthogonal subchannels using orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA). Let B be the total bandwidth and $b_m(t)$ that allocated to MD m in time slot t , then MD m 's achievable rate is: $\delta_m(t) = \log \det \left(\mathbf{I}_{\rho^e} + \frac{\mathbf{H}_m(t) \mathbf{H}_m^h(t)}{(\sigma^n)^2} \right)$. The transmission latency $\tau_m^t(t)$ is $\tau_m^t(t) = \frac{d_m(t)}{b_m(t) \delta_m(t)}$, where $d_m(t)$ is the data size of $\mathbf{x}_m^t(t)$. Given MD m 's transmission power, $p_m(t)$, its transmission energy is given by $E_m^t(t) = p_m(t) \tau_m^t(t)$.

C. Edge Server Computing Model

Upon reception at the ES, the signal undergoes demodulation and channel decoding, yielding the estimated bit stream $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_m^c(t)$. This stream is then processed through the dequantization module of the selected tail model, composed of the neural decoder, to reconstruct the features, and the analysis module to produce the final inference result. Let F^e represent the total computing capacity of the ES in each time slot, expressed as GPU frequency, and let $f_m^e(t)$ denote the GPU frequency allocated to MD m during time slot t . The edge computing latency of MD m in time slot t can then be written as: $\tau_m^e(t) = \frac{\psi_m^T(t)}{f_m^e(t) c^e \chi^e}$, where $\psi_m^T(t)$ is the FLOPs of the tail model corresponding to the head model selected by MD m , c^e and χ^e are the number of GPU cores and number of FLOPs per cycle per core of the ES, respectively. Similarly, the energy consumption is: $E_m^e(t) = \frac{\zeta^e (f_m^e(t))^2 \psi_m^t(t)}{c^e \chi^e}$, where ζ^e is the power consumption coefficient of the ES. We observe a trade-off in the allocation of computing resources: increasing the GPU frequency reduces processing latency, but this comes at the cost of higher energy consumption. The final inference result is then transmitted to MD m ; we denote by $\xi_m(t)$ the obtained inference accuracy. Notice that, since the data size of the tail model output is significantly smaller than the input, the downlink transmission latency is negligible in the computation of the total latency.

IV. DYNAMIC SPLIT DNN MODEL

The architecture of the proposed dynamic split DNN is shown in Fig. 3. It is a gated DNN where a gate structure controls the routing of the data and the activation of distinct sections of the model, called ‘‘branches’’. As explained later, the selection of the gate is controlled by a portion of the OMNIS distributed optimization engine. Individually, each branch is a split DNN sub-model consisting of L layers where we introduce a bottleneck layer at a specific point. This separates each sub-model into a head model \mathcal{H} with l layers and a tail model \mathcal{T} with $(L-l)$ layers. \mathcal{H} performs neural compression and quantization, transforming the tensor representation of the data into a more compact bit-wise format, thus trading off task performance with transmitted data payload. Next, we describe the head model, the gate unit, and the tail model in details.

Head Model. It resides at the MD and includes the set of l initial layers functioning as the neural encoder $\mathcal{H}(x)$, with x being an input sample, for semantic feature extraction. The neural encoder follows the structure of that in [10], which acts as a ‘‘neural compressor,’’ transforming the input sample into a small tensor representation. Notably, the neural encoder maps x to an intermediate output z . Such an output is what we refer to as the latent space, as we do not explicitly train z over a particularity targeted loss function. Instead, we let it be inferred by gradient propagation through the targeted reconstruction in the tail model. The head model also includes a quantization module after the neural encoder, which provides a compact representation of the output tensor. As shown in Fig. 2 and later in the results, quantization is key to achieve the desired tradeoff between data size on the one hand and resilience to bit error and task performance on the other.

Tail Model. It is deployed at the ES and is responsible for the final decision-making. It operates with two sets of decoders, thus functioning as the inverse of the head model. The first decoder is an algorithmic process of a dequantization module/process. The second is a neural decoder that uses teacher and student knowledge distillation [10] to reconstruct the received compressed features from z to a targeted j -th layer representation of a larger, non-split, teacher model as h_j . Specifically, it includes the neural decoder $f_{\text{dec}}(z)$, which decompresses the encoded input to recover an intermediate layer’s representation. Also, the remaining layers of the tail model are copied from the teacher model after the j -th layer for final inference.

Gate Unit. The proposed architecture enables the dynamic configuration of the split DNN setting through contextual gated model selection tied to the optimization engine. The gate controls the activated split DNN sub-model, which significantly impacts key performance metrics, such as energy consumption, delay, and accuracy. Notably, the gate meticulously selects the quantization method $\beta_m(t)$ and the number of quantization channels $\lambda_m(t)$ from predefined sets, to optimize the overall system performance. In addition to existing methods, we propose a novel quantization approach, called **Box quantization**. This method supports multiple quantization levels followed by source coding, enabling a dynamic and adaptive configuration prior to transmission. The proposed

Box quantization method is detailed next.

A. Proposed Box Quantization Method

The quantization method shown in Fig. 2, which we refer to as *standard* [10], is a basic form of 32-bit to 8-bit value representation through min-max normalization and multiplication of each value in the extracted semantic feature x' . The standard quantization method achieves a relatively low compression rate, resulting in a large payload size and increased transmission overhead. On the other hand, entropy quantization [20] can quantize the tensor to a significantly smaller size by leveraging techniques such as Huffman and arithmetic coding, producing a highly compact quantized representation z instead of x' . However, in entropy quantization, the loss of even a single bit can significantly alter the sequence's interpretation, causing a reading frame shift. This makes entropy quantization unsuitable for edge computing, where transmission is done over wireless channels that usually introduce errors.

To achieve a better trade-off between compression rate and bit error tolerance, we develop our resilient *Box* quantization scheme. Our method first applies the standard quantization on x and then performs a learnable Run-Length Encoding (RLE) to further reduce data size while ensuring effective dequantization. For the RLE process, the standard quantized tensor is first flattened into a vector x^q to facilitate sequential processing. Then the RLE reduces redundancy by storing each unique value in the sequence as a (value, frequency) pair in a byte stream, where the first byte represents the unique value and the second byte encodes the number of consecutive occurrences. To ensure efficient encoding without exceeding the standard byte size constraints, we use a bitdepth 8 to constrain the length of each pair to 255. Reshaping x^q in pairs of values and corresponding frequencies disrupts the gradient flow in the head model. To correctly decode x^q , the neural decoder applies the reconstruction loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}^c(x^q) = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^{|\mathbf{x}^q|-1} |x_{i+1}^q - x_i^q| \right)^2}{|\mathbf{x}^q| - 1} \times v. \quad (1)$$

The parameter v is a dynamic compression scaling factor that favors compressibility for high values at the cost of performance, while its lower values prioritize reconstruction accuracy. The function $\mathcal{L}^c(\cdot)$ minimizes the differences between consecutive values in \mathbf{x} , promoting sequences of identical values that reduce encoding size. However, excessive compression can lead to \mathbf{x} with uniform values, hindering accurate reconstruction of \mathbf{x} at the tail model.

B. Tradeoff Between Payload and Performance

To highlight the impact of different quantization methods on the inference performance, we conduct an evaluation experiment, and depict the accuracy versus payload size under varying SNR values in Fig. 4. For training in our Box quantization, we use $v \in \{0.15, 0.075, 0.0375\}$ for the bottleneck channel sizes of 12, 6, and 3 respectively. We show entropy-based quantization methods, "ENT", which follow the same near-exact neural architecture design as the standard autoencoder.

Fig. 4: Accuracy vs. payload size for different quantization methods at various SNRs: 3 dB (top-left), 5 dB (top-right), 7 dB (bottom-left), 10 dB (bottom-right).

However, their quantization function uses more advanced, and partially differentiable, coding methodologies like the range asymmetric numeral systems (rANS) approach [20].

Fig. 4 gives several key insights. On the one hand, entropy quantization is highly sensitive to bit errors, and even high-rate LDPC encoding cannot fully protect it. Any bit error leads to a drastic degradation in accuracy, often driving it close to zero. On the other hand, standard quantization strategies require the largest payload to attain the same accuracy. Box quantization falls in between, achieving a better trade-off between payload size and accuracy. Overall, no quantization scheme guarantees optimal performance under all conditions. This motivates us to formulate an optimization problem to dynamically control the whole pipeline jointly with resource allocation.

V. OMNIS OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

To achieve optimal system performance, gate unit control and RAN resource slicing should be jointly optimized based on task contexts and user channel conditions. Traditional centralized optimization algorithms adopted by other RAN slicing frameworks suffer from significant drawbacks, including a large solution space which leads to high computational complexity and a high risk of single points of failure. Also, the optimization objectives of MDs and the ES are inherently different. Typically, MDs act selfishly, viewing other MDs as competitors for limited resources and focusing solely on maximizing their own benefits. In contrast, the ES must consider overall network fairness, ensuring a balanced allocation of resources across all MDs. Due to these factors, formulating a global optimization problem is impractical. We thus formulate a gate unit control problem for each MD, and establish a RAN resource slicing problem for the ES. Let $\tau_m^s(t) = \tau_m^l(t) + \tau_m^t(t) + \tau_m^e(t)$ be the total latency and $E_m^s(t) = E_m^l(t) + E_m^t(t) + E_m^e(t)$ the total energy consumption. Define $\beta = \{\beta_m(t), m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$, $\lambda = \{\lambda_m(t), m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$, $\phi = \{\phi_m(t), m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$, $\mathbf{b} = \{b_m(t), m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$, and $\mathbf{f}^e = \{f_m^e(t), m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$. In the gate unit control problem, each MD aims to maximize its long-term average inference accuracy under latency and energy constraints, which is formulated as:

$$\text{P1: } \max_{\beta, \lambda} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{0 \leq t \leq T} \xi_m(t) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tau_m^s(t) \leq \tau_m^{\text{th}}(t), 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (2b)$$

$$E_m^s(t) \leq E_m^{\text{th}}(t), 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (2c)$$

where the QoS constraints (2b) and (2c) ensure that the total latency and energy consumption meet their respective target maximum values for ML tasks. In the RAN slicing problem, instead, the ES aims to maximize the minimum inference accuracy across all MDs under latency and energy constraints, by jointly optimizing the bandwidth and computing resource allocation and channel coding rate. The RAN slicing problem (P2) can then be formulated as:

$$\text{P2: } \max_{\phi, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{f}^e} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{0 \leq t \leq T} \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \xi_m(t) \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tau_m^s(t) \leq \tau_m^{\text{th}}(t), \forall m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (3b)$$

$$E_m^s(t) \leq E_m^{\text{th}}(t), \forall m \in \mathcal{M}, 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (3c)$$

$$\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} b_m(t) \leq B, 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (3d)$$

$$\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} f_m^e(t) \leq F^e, 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (3e)$$

Constraints (3d)–(3e) impose resource limits on the total available bandwidth B and computing capacity F^e across all MDs.

It can be seen that P1 is a nonlinear integer programming (NLIP) problem with discrete variables (β and λ), while P2 is a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem that involves intricate coupling among the discrete variables (ϕ) and the continuous variables (\mathbf{b} , \mathbf{f}^e). Both P1 and P2 are NP-hard. This can be proved by constructing a polynomial-time reduction from the generalized assignment problem (GAP)—a problem already known to be NP-hard.

Also, and most importantly, due to the lack of an analytical expression for the optimization objective in P1 and P2 (i.e., inference accuracy), conventional convex and non-convex optimization methods cannot be directly applied. Instead, as detailed next, we propose a distributed online optimization framework to iteratively solve P1 and P2.

A. Gate Unit Control on MDs

Multi-Agent Contextual Multi-armed Bandit (MAB) Formulation. In time slot t , every MD m has to solve the following problem:

$$\text{P1'}: \max_{\beta_m(t), \lambda_m(t)} \xi_m(t) \quad \text{s.t. } (2b), (2c). \quad (4)$$

In P1', an MD faces two uncertainties. It cannot predict (i) the resource allocation and channel coding rate chosen by the ES, impacting its accuracy, latency, and energy consumption, and (ii) the bit errors and packet loss due to the wireless channel, affecting feature integrity and making inference accuracy difficult to estimate. This decision-making process can be modeled as a multi-agent contextual MAB problem with the following properties: (i) finite, discrete configurations for MDs, (ii) the MDs' actions impact only the benefits they can get in the

current time slot, and (iii) the MDs can receive feedback to refine strategies in the current time slot. Next, we define the context, action, and reward space for such a problem.

(i) Context. Let $\mathbf{s}_m(t) \in \mathcal{S}$ be MD m 's context at time t , including task requirements and estimated achievable rate $\mathbf{s}_m(t) = \{\tau_m^{\text{th}}(t), E_m^{\text{th}}(t), \omega_m^{\text{l}}(t), \omega_m^{\text{e}}(t), \hat{\delta}_m(t)\}$. MDs estimate the CSI via uplink pilots and ES's feedback, to obtain $\hat{\delta}_m(t)$.

(ii) Arms. Each arm corresponds to a branch of the dynamic split DNN model. The arm $\mathbf{a}_m(t) \in \mathcal{A}$ chosen by MD m at time t is $\mathbf{a}_m(t) = (\beta_m(t), \lambda_m(t))$, with $|\mathcal{A}| = |\mathcal{B}| \times |\mathcal{L}|$.

(iii) Rewards. After resource slicing and ML task execution, the MDs receive from the ES: the accuracy $\xi_m(t)$, transmission latency $\tau_m^{\text{l}}(t)$, edge processing latency $\tau_m^{\text{e}}(t)$, and transmission energy consumption $E_m^{\text{l}}(t)$. Latency and energy consumption targets are treated as soft constraints. By denoting with $\text{erf}(\cdot)$ the Gaussian error function, the reward $r_m(t)$ is given by:

$$r_m(t) = \xi_m(t) + \omega_m^{\text{l}}(t) \text{erf}(\tau_m^{\text{th}}(t) - \tau_m^{\text{s}}(t)) + \omega_m^{\text{e}}(t) \text{erf}(E_m^{\text{th}}(t) - E_m^{\text{s}}(t)). \quad (5)$$

Bayesian Optimization for Solving P1'. The reward function in P1' is non-linear, with rewards for different gate unit control decisions being correlated. Small changes in $\beta_m(t)$ or $\lambda_m(t)$ lead to gradual shifts in system latency, energy consumption, and accuracy. This correlation allows us to infer unobserved context-action pairs, reducing exploration overhead. As MDs must make decisions without knowing the ES's strategy, prior knowledge of action-reward likelihoods is beneficial. We adopt the Gaussian process-based upper-confidence-bound (GP-UCB) algorithm, modeling the reward function as samples from a Gaussian process (GP) over the context-action space. The upper confidence bound (UCB) algorithm is used to select the best action. Let $z \in \mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A}$ denote a context-action pair, and $z_m(t)$ the context-action pair of MD m at time slot t . Let $GP(\mu_m(z), k_m(z, z'))$ be the GP function estimator for the reward function, where $\mu_m(z)$ is the mean function and $k_m(z, z')$ is the covariance function or the kernel of MD m . Assume a zero mean prior with bounded variance less than 1. Let $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_m(t) = \{\hat{r}_m(1), \dots, \hat{r}_m(t)\}$ denote the noisy reward sample vector, with Gaussian noise $N(0, (\sigma^n)^2)$. In time slot t , MD m updates the posterior distribution of the reward function GP by:

$$\mu_m(z) \leftarrow \mathbf{k}_m(z, z_m(t))^\top (\mathbf{K}_m + (\sigma^n)^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_m(t), \quad (6)$$

$$k_m(z, z') \leftarrow k_m(z, z') - \mathbf{k}_m(z, z_m(t))$$

$$\times (\mathbf{K}_m(z_m(t)) + (\sigma^n)^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{k}_m(z, z_m(t)), \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_m(z, z_m(t)) = [k_m(z, z_m(1)), \dots, k_m(z, z_m(t))]^\top$ and we use $\mathbf{K}_m(z_m(t)) = [k_m(z, z')]_{z, z' \in \mathcal{Z}_m(t)}$ to denote the covariance vector and the kernel matrix. Based on the posterior distribution, the MDs can estimate the unobserved values of $z \in \mathcal{Z}$. Similarly to [21], we adopt a kernel satisfying stationarity and anisotropy. The distance between two context-action pair z and z' is given by $\sqrt{(z-z')^\top \mathbf{L}^{-2}(z-z')}$, where $\mathbf{L} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{l})$ is a diagonal matrix, and \mathbf{l} is the length-scale

vector. Using the anisotropic Matérn kernel [22], the kernel function for the reward function GP of MD m is:

$$k_m(z, z') = \left(1 + \sqrt{3(z - z')^\top \mathbf{L}^{-2}(z - z')}\right) \times \exp\left(-\sqrt{3(z - z')^\top \mathbf{L}^{-2}(z - z')}\right). \quad (8)$$

Given the context-action set, MD m leverages the UCB policy as the acquisition function to select the dynamic DNN parameters as:

$$\mathbf{a}_m(t) = \arg \max_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} \left[\mu_m(z) + \sqrt{\omega_m^a(t) k_m(z, z')} \right], \quad (9)$$

where $\omega_m^a(t)$ is a dynamic weight that controls the trade-off between exploration and exploitation. Specifically, we select $\omega_m^a(t)$ based on an upper bound of the Reproductive Kernel Hilbert Space (RKHS) norm and the maximum mutual information gain from past observations (see [22] for the specific formula). To evaluate the performance of different acquisition functions, the UCB-based acquisition function can be replaced with Thompson sampling (TS) [23]. Instead of selecting actions based on the upper confidence bound in (9), TS samples from the posterior distribution of the reward function and selects the action that maximizes the sampled value. Notably, the TS-based acquisition function can be written as: $\mathbf{a}_m(t) = \arg \max_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} \tilde{\mu}_m(z)$, where $\tilde{\mu}_m(z)$ is a sample drawn from the posterior distribution of the reward function. TS can be considered as another deployment version of OMNIS.

Next, we analyze the regret performance of the multi-agent GP-UCB algorithm. Let the optimal and actual expected rewards in time slot t for MD m be $\max_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{E}[r_m(t) | \mathbf{s}_m(t)]$ and $\mathbb{E}[r_m(t) | \mathbf{s}_m(t), \mathbf{a}_m(t)]$, respectively. The regret for MD m is $R_m(t) = \max_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{E}[r_m(t) | \mathbf{s}_m(t)] - \mathbb{E}[r_m(t) | \mathbf{s}_m(t), \mathbf{a}_m(t)]$. The cumulative regret over T time slots for MD m is $R_m^T = \sum_{t=1}^T R_m(t)$, while the system's cumulative regret is $R^T = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} R_m^T$. Theorem 1 provides the expression for R^T when using the GP-UCB algorithm.

Theorem 1. *The system cumulative regret R^T for gate unit control can be obtained for any $T \geq 1$ as:*

$$P\left(R^t \leq M \left(\sqrt{\frac{8T\omega^a(T)\gamma^T}{\log(1+(\sigma^n)^{-2})} + 2} \right)\right) \geq 1 - M\eta, \quad (10)$$

where $\eta \in (0, 1)$, $\gamma^T = \mathcal{O}\left(\tau^{\frac{\dim(\mathbf{z})(\dim(\mathbf{z})+1)}{3+\dim(\mathbf{z})(\dim(\mathbf{z})+1)}} \log T\right)$, $\dim(\mathbf{z})$ is the dimension of \mathbf{z} that satisfies $\dim(\mathbf{z}) = \dim(\mathbf{a}_m(t)) + \dim(\mathbf{s}_m(t))$.

Proof. Using the Matérn kernel, the individual regret bound for MD m is given in [21], [22], as:

$$P\left(R_m^t \leq \sqrt{\frac{8T\omega^a(T)\gamma^T}{\log(1+(\sigma^n)^{-2})} + 2}\right) \geq 1 - \eta, \quad \forall T \geq 1.$$

Since each MD operates independently under the same regret bound, using the Boole's inequality (union bound), the probability that at least one MD violates this bound is at most $M \cdot \eta$. Summing over all MDs, we get the regret bound as in (10). \square

B. RAN Resource Slicing on ES

Before MD m transmits the head model output to the ES, it first sends the task requirements $\{\tau_m^{th}(t), E_m^{th}(t), \omega_m^t(t), \omega_m^e(t)\}$, the gate unit control results $\mathbf{a}_m(t)$, the local processing latency $\tau_m^l(t)$, and the energy consumption $E_m^l(t)$ to the ES for solving P2. Upon receiving this data from the MDs, in every time slot t the ES solves the following problem:

$$P2' : \max_{\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{f}^e(t), \phi(t)} \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \xi_m(t) \quad s.t. \quad (3b), (3c), (3d), (3e). \quad (11)$$

The coupling between continuous $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{f}^e)$ and discrete (ϕ) variables still makes the problem intractable. Thus, using the BCD method, we further decompose P2' into three sub-problems: (i) bandwidth allocation, (ii) GPU frequency allocation, and (iii) channel coding rate selection. Each sub-problem is solved alternately by fixing the other two variables until convergence, i.e., the stabilization of decision variables and the overall objective value across iterations, or the algorithm reaching a predefined maximum number of iterations. Notably, the closed-form solution of sub-problem (i) can be obtained using the Lagrange multiplier method; sub-problem (ii) can be efficiently solved using off-the-shelf convex optimization tools such as CVXPY; sub-problem (iii) can be solved by exhaustive search. This decomposition enables scalable optimization even under complex coupling between variables.

Note that the ES's resource allocation does not affect the inference accuracy of MDs when other variables are fixed. The ES's objective is to minimize QoS soft constraint violations (3b) and (3c), while satisfying resource capacity hard constraints (3d)—(3e), given the gate unit control strategy $\mathbf{a}_m(t)$ and initial channel coding rate $\phi^{[0]}(t)$. By incorporating the QoS constraints and removing the irrelevant term (inference accuracy $\xi_m(t)$), the bandwidth allocation problem in time slot t becomes:

$$P2.1' : \min_{\mathbf{b}(t)} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d_m(t) (\omega_m^t + \omega_m^e p_m(t))}{b_m(t) \log \det \left(\mathbf{I}_{\rho^e} + \frac{\mathbf{H}_m(t) \mathbf{H}_m^H(t)}{(\sigma^n)^2} \right)} \quad (12a)$$

$$s.t. \quad (3d), 0 \leq b_m(t) \leq B, b_m(t) \in \mathbb{R}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}. \quad (12b)$$

Let $d'_m(t) = \frac{d_m(t) (\omega_m^t + \omega_m^e p_m(t))}{\log \det \left(\mathbf{I}_{\rho^e} + \frac{\mathbf{H}_m(t) \mathbf{H}_m^H(t)}{(\sigma^n)^2} \right)}$. We build a Lagrange function $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}, \iota^b)$ by incorporating constraint (3d) into (12a):

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}, \iota^b) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d'_m(t)}{b_m(t)} + \iota^b \left(\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} b_m(t) - B \right), \quad (13)$$

where ι^b is a Lagrange multiplier. Taking the partial derivative of $b_m(t)$ and setting $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}, \iota^b) = 0$, we have $b_m^*(t) = \sqrt{d'_m(t) / \iota^b}$. Based on constraint (3d), we have $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{d'_m(t)}{\iota^b} = B$. Then we can obtain $\iota^b = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sqrt{d'_m(t)}$, thus the optimal bandwidth allocation strategy is $b_m^*(t) = B \sqrt{d'_m(t)} / \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sqrt{d'_m(t)}$.

Similarly, the computing resource allocation problem in time slot t can be written as:

$$\text{P2.2}' : \min_{\mathbf{f}^e(t)} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \left(\frac{\omega_m^t \psi_m^t(t)}{f_m^e(t) c^e \chi^e} + \frac{\omega_m^e \zeta^e (f_m^e(t))^2 \psi_m^t(t)}{c^e \chi^e} \right), \quad (14a)$$

$$\text{s.t. (3e), } 0 \leq f_m(t) \leq F^e, c_m(t) \in \mathbb{R}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}. \quad (14b)$$

The first term in the above sum is convex with respect to $f_m^e(t)$ since it has the form of an inverse function, which is convex for positive values. The second term is also convex, as it is a quadratic function of $f_m^e(t)$. Since the sum of convex functions is still convex, so is the objective function. Further, the constraint (3e) is linear, thus the feasible set is convex. Hence, P2.2' is convex and can be efficiently solved using solvers such as CVXPY.

Given the gate unit control strategy and the resource allocation strategy, the ES then has to solve the following channel coding rate selection problem:

$$\text{P2.3}' : \max_{\phi_m(t)} \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \xi_m(t) \quad \text{s.t. (3b), (3c)}. \quad (15)$$

Importantly, since the other variables are fixed, the channel coding rate selected by the ES for MD m does not affect the accuracy, latency, or energy consumption of other MDs. Thus, the ES can independently determine each MD's channel coding rate, and an exhaustive search over all possible coding rates can be performed. The ES aims to select the coding rate that maximizes inference accuracy while satisfying the QoS constraints (3b) and (3c). If no rate satisfies the constraints, the ES chooses the one minimizing the penalty term in (5). To determine inference accuracy for a selected rate, the ES can use pre-computed accuracy curves under different SNR and payload conditions to guide decision-making. The overall computing complexity to solve P1 and P2 by using the proposed optimization framework is given in Theorem 2.

Theorem 2. *Assuming that P2' requires τ° iterations to converge, the total computing complexity of solving P1 and P2 for T time slots is $\mathcal{O}(M(T^4 + T|\mathcal{A}| + \tau^\circ(T + |\Phi| + M^2T)))$.*

Proof. In slot t , the GP-UCB algorithm updates the GP model for each MD m , involving matrix inversions and kernel computations with complexity $\mathcal{O}(t^3)$ [22]. Computing the UCB values adds $\mathcal{O}(t)$, and action selection over a discrete space \mathcal{A} contributes $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{A}|)$. With M MDs, the total complexity of the multi-agent GP-UCB algorithm is thus $\mathcal{O}(Mt^3 + M|\mathcal{A}|)$. Meanwhile, the ES allocates bandwidth resources by solving P2.1' with complexity $\mathcal{O}(M)$. Using Interior-Point Method in CVXPY, P2.2' becomes a second-order cone programming (SOCP), whose complexity is $\mathcal{O}(M^3)$. Since the channel coding rate can be selected independently for each MD, the complexity of solving P2.3' is $\mathcal{O}(M|\Phi|)$. Summing over T time slots $\sum_{t=1}^T t^3 = \mathcal{O}(T^4)$, the total complexity is $\mathcal{O}(MT^4 + MT|\mathcal{A}| + MT\tau^\circ + M\tau^\circ|\Phi| + M^3T\tau^\circ) = \mathcal{O}(M(T^4 + T|\mathcal{A}| + \tau^\circ(T + |\Phi| + M^2T)))$. Although the complexity expression involves T^4 , our evaluation shows that the proposed algorithm converges swiftly. \square

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Experimental Settings. We assume that the MDs are randomly distributed within a 250 m radius circle of the ES. Each MD's GPU frequency, cores, and FLOPs per cycle are uniformly distributed in [1.2, 2] GHz, [512, 1024], and [8, 16], respectively. The ES's GPU frequency, cores, and FLOPs per cycle are uniformly distributed in [3, 5] GHz, [8192, 16384], and [16, 32], respectively. The MDs and the ES have $N_m=4$ and $N_e=64$ antennas, respectively, and the system uses 100 kHz bandwidth. In each time slot t , latency and energy thresholds are sampled as $\tau_m^{th}(t) \sim \mathcal{U}(0.8, 1.5)$ second and $E_m^{th}(t) \sim \mathcal{U}(0.8, 1.5)$ J. The latency preference weight is $\omega_m^t(t) \sim 1.5 \times \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$, with $\omega_m^e(t) = 1 - \omega_m^t(t)$. MDs' mobility is modeled using the random point mobility model with initial random placement and speed sampled from $\mathcal{U}(10, 20)$ m/s. MIMO channel coefficients include large-scale fading following the log-distance model, $128.1 + 37.6 \log_{10}(d)$ dB, and small-scale Rayleigh fading. AWGN is modeled as $\mathcal{N}(0, -174 + 10 \log_{10}(B))$ dBm. BPSK modulation and LDPC encoding are used, with LDPC coding rate ϕ selected from $\{1, 2/3, 5/6\}$. We set the variance of the channel estimation error matrix to $\sigma^h=0.5$.

Each MD performs semantic segmentation on a single image per time slot. We use the COCO dataset [5], which includes 80 object categories with bounding boxes and segmentation masks. Model performance is evaluated using the COCO mAP score, calculated over IOUs from 50% to 95% at 5% intervals (mAP@[0.5:0.95]). The proposed dynamic DNN is based on Mask R-CNN with a ResNet50 backbone. The neural encoder has four convolutional layers: the first follows ResNet50's initial structure with batch normalization, ReLU, and MaxPooling, while the next two use stride-2 convolutions for downsampling. For the tail model, we set the j -th layer as the output of ResNet-50's first block, with reconstruction loss in (1) applied to the outputs of the remaining three blocks. The decoder reconstructs features via two deconvolutional layers and two convolutional layers. GDN aids renormalization for rANS, while Box quantization follows a standard bottleneck structure. Given the entropy quantization's sensitivity to bit errors, we use only standard and Box quantization in experiments, with three quantization settings: 3, 6, and 12 channels. We distill knowledge from a Mask R-CNN model (mAP 41.80%) to train both the head and tail models following the two-stage process defined in [10].

Benchmarks. We compare OMNIS against three benchmarks, modified or extended from state-of-the-art RAN slicing frameworks for fair comparison. Notice that our scheme is labeled as "OMNIS-UCB" or "OMNIS-TS", depending on whether UCB or TS is used as action acquisition function.

- *Greedy-based Optimization (GDO)* [2], [8]: SEM-O-RAN [8] is modified by replacing its "data compression scaling factor" with the compression mechanism of our dynamic DNN model. The ES employs a greedy algorithm to select dynamic quantization parameters. Initially, the ES randomly assigns neural network parameters to each MD and solves P2'. It then reallocates models, assigning less (more) compressed models to MDs with the lowest (highest) accuracy, iteratively solving

Fig. 5: Convergence of different schemes: average reward (top-left), latency (top-middle), accuracy (top-right), energy consumption (bottom-left), violation probability (bottom-middle), and average violation excess (bottom-right).

Fig. 6: Average performance for varying SNR values.

$P2'$ until no further improvement in the objective is possible.

- *Resource Slicing with Static Models (RSS)* [24]: RSS employs a static version of the proposed inference model. Specifically, each MD’s quantization parameters and channel coding rate remain fixed across all time slots, thus requiring only the ES to solve $P2'$ in each slot.

- *Centralized Optimization (CTO)* [21]: CTO implements a centralized contextual MAB agent at the ES. In each slot, the ES employs the GP-UCB and BCD algorithms to iteratively solve $P1'$ and $P2'$. The objective of $P1'$ is modified to align with $P2'$ for centralized optimization.

We now analyze the performance of different schemes under various parameter settings. We focus on the reward, latency, energy consumption, inference accuracy, QoS constraint violation probability, and constraint violation excess (how much QoS constraints are violated). All evaluation results are averaged over 3 runs.

Convergence Performance. Fig. 5 compares the performance of all schemes, averaged over 8 MDs and 200 time slots. OMNIS (including OMNIS-TS and OMNIS-UCB, which perform nearly identically) shows fast convergence—rewards and accuracy stabilize within 30 slots, while latency and energy consumption also reach steady values. OMNIS achieves the highest inference accuracy and optimal overall reward with near-optimal latency and energy. Although the centralized optimization (CTO) eventually reaches similar performance, its runtime is about 13x longer. OMNIS also significantly reduces QoS violations and over-expenditure, offering more stable performance across time. In contrast, RSS and GDO fail to adapt to dynamic context changes, leading to suboptimal performance.

Average Performance Under Different SNRs. Fig. 6

Fig. 7: Average performance for different MD numbers.

shows the average performance as the SNR varies, with 5 MDs over 200 time slots. For higher SNRs, transmission rates grow and the BER decreases, resulting in lower latency, energy consumption, and better inference accuracy. OMNIS consistently achieves the highest reward and accuracy. While its latency and energy are slightly higher at high SNR, it maintains a low QoS violation probability, efficiently utilizing resources within constraints. Also, OMNIS-UCB improves accuracy by up to 11.92% and reduces the QoS violation probability and excess by up to 11.3x and 15.2x (resp.) over RSS.

Average Performance for a Varying Number of MDs.

Fig. 7 illustrates performance as the number of MDs increases. Resource contention at the ES intensifies, increasing delay and reducing average reward. Although transmission energy rises with delay, the dominant computing energy, proportional to the square of GPU frequency, drops due to frequency sharing. For more than 6 MDs, QoS violations surge, prompting selection of higher-compression models and reducing accuracy. OMNIS, however, scales well, achieving the best rewards, highest accuracy, and minimal QoS violations even with more than 6 MDs. Compared to RSS, OMNIS-UCB improves accuracy by up to 22.85% and reduces QoS violation probability and excess by up to 12.5x and 2.9x, respectively.

Adaptive Model Slicing Results. Fig. 8 shows the top-3 most selected models under varying SNRs and MD counts. As SNR increases or MDs decrease, OMNIS selects Standard-12 more frequently for its higher payload and accuracy. Better channel conditions allow larger payloads within QoS constraints, enabling use of low-compression models. Under poor SNR or high MD density, OMNIS adapts by selecting more compressed models (e.g., Box-6), balancing inference performance and QoS constraints. This demonstrates OMNIS’s capability to dynamically select optimal models based on system conditions.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed OMNIS, a semantic slicing framework for edge computing. OMNIS overcomes the limitations of static slicing by leveraging dynamic split neural networks for adaptive quantization and bit error resilience. Notably, we introduced “Box quantization” to ensure efficient and reliable task offloading. To optimize the system performance, we formulated two optimization problems for MDs and the ES. The former maximizes inference accuracy under latency and energy constraints using a multi-agent contextual MAB algorithm.

Fig. 8: Model pick probability for SNR=2 dB (top-left), 4 dB (top-middle), 6 dB (top-right), and 2 (bottom-left), 4 (bottom-middle), 6 (bottom-right) MDs.

The latter maximizes the fairness of inference accuracy via the BCD method with convex optimization. Our results show that OMNIS improves inference accuracy by up to 22.85% while significantly reducing the QoS constraint violation probability by up to 10x.

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